

Journal club

DECISION-MAKING

MEASURING AND ENHANCING INTUITION

As the world becomes more complex and uncertain, insights into how people decide are crucial. Intuition—the ability to use nonconscious information for conscious decision making—represents an invaluable trainable skill to improve decision making. However, scientific tools to measure intuition are scant, and insight into how intuition can be deliberately enhanced is even rarer.

In 2016, Galang Lufityanto, Chris Donkin, and Joel Pearson used a psychophysical paradigm to measure intuition. In a random-dot motion task, participants were asked to report the global motion direction (right or left) of moving dots while positive and negative emotional images were flashed to one of their eyes. Although this emotional image was presented below the threshold for conscious awareness, it could support more accurate decisions because the emotional valence of the image (positive or negative) was 100% predictive of dot motion direction.

Across four experiments, accuracy, speed, and confidence in the motion direction decision task were higher when emotional stimuli were presented subliminally compared to when a scrambled image was presented subliminally. These results support the hypothesis that unconscious emotions can influence behavior; in other words, there is an effect of intuition.

One striking finding was that there was no significant difference in decision accuracy improvement between negative and positive subliminal images, despite the known asymmetry in salience between those emotions. Thus, it was not the mere presence of emotion but rather the specific relationship between emotional valence and motion direction that allowed participants to use nonconscious emotional information to improve decision accuracy.

For me, the most interesting aspect of Lufityanto et al.'s research is the discovery of a nonconscious effect of learning on intuition. The authors explain that

participants established intuition from consistent pairings between both conscious (the moving dots) and nonconscious (the emotional images) sources of information. Participants' decision accuracy improved over time without any immediate performance feedback, which suggests that people can boost their intuition with practice.

Perhaps the finding related to intuition's training potential is not unexpected, as researchers generally agree that intuition can be trained over time. However, the technique Lufityanto et al. used lays vital groundwork for future investigations into how intuition can be deliberately trained.

As a scholar who has long been fascinated by intuitive decision making, I am immensely energized by the opportunity to identify and refine methods to enhance intuition to improve rapid decision making. For instance, future work could test whether subliminal emotional images could be used to train people to improve their intuition across diverse real-world decision-making tasks.

Thus, the paper by Lufityanto et al. did not merely provide a paradigm to measure and potentially enhance intuition. It also opened the possibility of harnessing intuition's unexploited potential to become as critical as the analytical mind for accurate decision-making. This balance between analytic thinking and intuition is crucial for the future.

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